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Poultry farming development in Russia: analysis of the current state and development trends

KEYWORDS

poultry farming,
poultry industry,
global production,
poultry meat production,
egg production,
food safety,
rational consumption norm

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The development of poultry farming in Russia is crucial for meeting domestic demand for meat and eggs, reducing import dependence, enhancing food security, and advancing agricultural growth.

This article is aimed at analyzing the current state of poultry farming development in the Russian Federation and outlining the prospects for this industry.

Materials and methods. The materials used in the study were as follows: data from periodicals on poultry farming trends in Russia, statistical reports from the Russian Federation, its regions, and the Ministry of Agriculture of Russia over recent decades. The study employed abstract-logical, monographic, computational-constructive, comparative analysis, and statistical methods.

Results. It has been established that over the past decade, poultry farming has been developing rapidly in many countries, including Russia. In Russia, from 2016 to 2021, poultry meat production increased by 838.26 thousand tons (or 20%), while egg production reached 2,357 thousand tons in 2017. In subsequent years, up to and including 2021, egg production remained unchanged. The achieved level is quite high, with an average of 313 eggs per laying hen per year, given that the zootechnical productivity standard for egg-laying hens is approximately 300 eggs per year. Thus, Russia ensures poultry meat production of 34.2 kg per capita, which is 10.3% higher than the rational recommended norm (31 kg per year), while egg production has reached 308 eggs per capita, exceeding the rational recommended norm (260 eggs per year) by 18.5%.

Conclusion. The development of poultry farming in Russia contributes to increased production of poultry meat and eggs, providing the population with high-quality products and reducing import dependence. This industry can stimulate regional economic growth, create new jobs, and improve living standards. The adoption of modern technologies will enhance production efficiency, improve product quality, and reduce environmental impact. Research in poultry nutrition will optimize feed resources, reduce costs, and increase productivity.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the article stems from the fact that poultry farming is one of the most critical sectors of agriculture, providing the population with essential food products, including poultry meat and eggs. In addition, poultry farming is considered a profitable and quickly recoupable agricultural sector. In many countries worldwide, particularly in Russia, poultry and eggs are popular food products with stable consumer demand. Moreover, poultry products have significant export potential.

The first mention of domestic chickens dates back to the 10th century, as evidenced by archaeological excavations conducted in the country. Archaeologists discovered bird remains and their depictions on scrolls and pottery. The first book dedicated to poultry farming was published in 1774, providing detailed information on bird breeding and the development of new breeds. Another book on the subject was released in 1790. The most distinguished poultry farmer of that time was I.I. Abozin, who authored numerous books and articles on poultry breeding. He was the first to classify chicken breeds, and his classification system is still in use today [1].

From the 15th to the 19th century, poultry farming was considered the most backward agricultural sector. Birds were primarily raised by peasants, mainly for their landlords. However, starting in the 1860s, new productive poultry breeds began to be imported from abroad, marking a new milestone in the industry's development [8–10].

Poultry numbers began to rise sharply in 1913 but suffered significant losses with the onset of the Civil War in 1914. From 1918 to 1920, the industry actively recovered. Over the next decade, large poultry farms focused on raising chicks and breeding new breeds were established. Starting in the 1930s, poultry research centers were created across the country, intensifying the sector's development.

During the Great Patriotic War, poultry farming faced huge losses once again. By 1955, the industry began to recover, and nine years later, scientists noted the prerequisites for intensive growth. In 1961, new poultry breeds were introduced from Europe, initiating active hybridization. Four years later, hybrid poultry began contributing significantly to the country's economy [2].

From 1971 onward, the material and technical base of industrial poultry farming strengthened. New feed production technologies, equipment, and breeding methods were adopted, increasing poultry numbers. By 1990, production turnover

reached such a pace that the industry became one of the leaders in agriculture. However, due to agricultural reforms in the 1990s, domestic poultry products lost popularity due to uncontrolled import growth. Starting in 2000, the current government began correcting past mistakes by supporting poultry farming. A key step was the establishment of the All-Russian Poultry Union, uniting all enterprises related to the industry [3].

Poultry farming is a vital agricultural sector tasked with supplying the population with dietary foods including eggs and poultry meat, which are rich in animal protein while being low in calories. Poultry meat and eggs account for over 27% of total protein consumption. The steadily growing demand for poultry meat and eggs is attributed to their consumer properties and lower prices compared to other livestock products. In recent years, the Russian government has paid close attention to poultry farming development [4].

This study was aimed at analyzing the current state of poultry farming development in the Russian Federation and outline prospects for the industry's growth.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials included data from periodicals on poultry farming development trends in Russia, statistical reports from the Russian Federation, its constituent entities, and the Ministry of Agriculture of Russia over recent decades. The study employed abstract-logical, monographic, computational-constructive, comparative analysis, and statistical methods.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to W. Hongguang, meat consumption is one of the most important indicators of dietary quality. Global production and consumption of livestock products have increased significantly over the past 60 years. Meat production has increased 3.8-fold, dairy products 1.6-fold, and egg production 4.6-fold [5].

M. E. Eda et al. indicate that geese domestication began approximately 7,000 years ago, making geese the oldest domesticated poultry species in history [6].

H. Pingel and L. Germany highlight the high nutritional value of waterfowl meat and eggs as human food, emphasizing their optimal essential amino acid composition, favorable fatty acid profile with a high percentage of polyunsaturated fatty acids, and a balanced omega-6 to omega-3 ratio [7].

R. N. Chatterjee et al. state that poultry farming is the fastest-growing agricultural sector globally, with significant expansion rates in recent years. Poultry products such as eggs and meat are high-quality food sources rich in macro- and micronutrients with high vitamin bioavailability. Poultry farming provides a stable income during crises such as crop failure, drought, or disease. Small-scale poultry rearing serves as a means of ensuring food security in many underdeveloped and developing countries [8].

D. Sapkota and K. Begum describe integrated duck breeding systems practiced worldwide due to their advantages, such as the duck-rice-fish-azolla system. In this model, part of the duck shelter is built over a pond, allowing manure and spilled feed to fall directly into the pond. Duck droppings act as an organic fertilizer for plankton production, while spilled feed particles serve as fish food. At the same time, nutrients from the pond enrich rice fields through irrigation [9].

S. Nikolaev et al. argue that complete and balanced feeding has a significant impact on environmental sustainability and is the foundation of high poultry productivity and efficient nutrient conversion. Since feed costs constitute the primary expense in poultry meat production, the authors stress the importance of finding cheaper and more efficient energy sources while maintaining dietary balance [10].

S. Smolentsev et al. present findings on the efficacy of plant-based bioactive supplements containing succinic and fumaric acids in commercial poultry farming. Their study demonstrated that adding these supplements to broiler diets improved flock survival rates and increased average live weight gain by up to 15%, depending on the supplement type [11].

O. Krotova et al. emphasize that the availability of high-quality yet affordable compound feeds largely determines the development level and economics of poultry farming. The authors consider that one of the main tasks of the country's agro-industrial complex is to provide the population with high-quality food products. Given the need for accelerated import substitution and reducing the agricultural sector's dependence on expensive imported feed components, it is essential to explore locally available, low-cost traditional and non-traditional feed resources [12].

M. de Mesquita Souza Saraiva et al. note that global demand for animal protein is constantly increasing, and food animals, particularly broiler chickens, play a key role in the global food supply. The authors highlight critical aspects of antimicrobial resistance emergence and spread in the poultry industry and its impact on public health from a global perspective [13].

J. M. Bettridge et al. report significant interest in utilizing local genetic resources to produce environmentally sustainable chickens, while simultaneously providing the basis for an economically sustainable enterprise. The authors argue that sustainable poultry development measures for small-scale farmers, including breeding programs, should be adapted to local conditions and designed for flexible implementation [14].

M. I. El Sabry and O. Almasri consider the impact of stocking density on social, feeding, and sexual behavior. According to the authors, the fish and waterfowl production system can become a promising and sustainable solution for increasing waterfowl production, maintaining bird welfare, and conserving energy, among other benefits [15].

E. M. Idamokoro and Y. S. Hosu investigate village poultry production as a tool for ensuring food security [16].

The prospects for poultry farming development in Russia appear positive due to growing domestic demand, advancements in technology, and government support. Expected outcomes include increased production, genetic improvements, and enhanced export potential.

A. Chertova states food security represents one of the most critical elements of Russia's national security. Food security forms the foundation for preserving sovereignty, serves as an important aspect of demographic policy, and directly impacts the population's living standards and quality of life [17].

O. Verbitskaya analyzes the agrarian reform of the 1990s in Russia. The author demonstrated that the agrarian reform, intended to significantly improve agricultural efficiency, failed to meet expectations. The set objectives were not achieved, and in practice, they only devastated the agricultural sector. Over ten years of market reforms, cultivated areas substantially decreased, livestock numbers declined, production fell by more than 50%, and labor mechanization levels dropped by approximately 33%. As a result of 1990s market reforms, Russia's agricultural sector regressed by 30-40 years in key performance indicators [18].

Prospects for applying new technologies to poultry farming include improved efficiency, enhanced bird health, reduced costs and environmental impact, as well as advancements in automation and genetics.

A. Haldar et al. report that numerous digital technologies now exist for smart and precision livestock farming. The livestock sector has become a hotspot for

implementing advanced technologies to monitor farm animals in real-time, optimize feed consumption, predict diseases, and improve animal health [19].

Y. Zhao and X. Yang state that intelligent poultry farming management uses multiple sensors, analytics, visualization, and communication technologies to aid decision-making and optimize farm management [20].

The study by R. P. Soesanto et al. focuses on designing and developing an IoT-based tool for weighing poultry on farms to monitor and control coop conditions [21].

V. Tikiwala et al. demonstrate the applicability of machine learning models for automated egg production forecasting in poultry farming systems. In developing this predictive machine learning model, the authors employed ARIMA time-series analysis, achieving 59.21% accuracy in monthly analysis [22].

A. Y. Izmailov et al. describe a successful case of implementing digital monitoring and management technologies developed on an intelligent analytical software platform to address agroecological challenges. The authors have created an interactive program designed for monitoring livestock/poultry waste (manure) management and coordinating the use of resulting organic fertilizers while considering environmental and economic indicators [23].

M. V. Zapevalov has developed technological regulations for manure processing to produce fuel briquettes and organomineral fertilizers, conducting research and development to establish production lines for these products. This manure utilization technology provides enterprises with energy-saving, agrochemical, economic, environmental, and social benefits [24].

A. N. Kislyakov et al. assert that government regulation in poultry farming serves as an important factor in ensuring national food security and enhancing food availability for the population. According to the authors, government regulation helps maintain economic parity between livestock sectors, protects and supports domestic poultry producers, and aims to stabilize and improve production economic efficiency [25].

Thus, the analyzed sources emphasize the significance of poultry farming as a crucial sector for food security. Global production of meat, eggs, and dairy products has grown substantially in recent decades, with waterfowl being particularly valuable due to their nutritional composition. There exists fragmented experience in implementing innovative systems, biological additives, and digital technologies to enhance production. In Russia, industry development is associated with growing domestic demand, adoption of new technologies, genetic improvements, and reduced dependence on imported feed.

RESULTS

Due to the dynamic growth of the global population, providing adequate food supplies, particularly of animal origin, becomes increasingly challenging each year. It is known that the planet faces food shortages: approximately one billion people suffer from undernourishment annually, with 17 million dying from hunger, including 2.7 million children. In this context, poultry farming plays a crucial role through its production of meat and eggs. According to FAO projections, the annual growth rate of poultry meat production by 2025 will reach 3.1%, compared to 2.6% for pork, 1.3% for beef, and 0.2% for other meat types [18-20].

According to FAO, in 2021, global meat production reached 335.33 million tons, of which: 135.07 million tons (40.3%) was poultry meat, 112.86 million tons (33.7%) was pork, 70.37 million tons (21%) was beef and veal, 16.20 million tons (4.8%) was mutton, and only 0.83 million tons (0.2%) came from other animal sources (see Table 1). This demonstrates that poultry farming holds a significant position in meeting global demand for meat and meat products [26].

Table 1

Global meat production in 2016-2021, million tons

Production	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
In total	317.80	321.35	331.34	329.95	326.59	335.33
Poultry meat	115.19	117.98	123.21	125.64	132.07	135.07
Pork	118.4	118.08	120.71	117.84	106.53	112.86
Beef	69.11	69.94	71.72	70.38	71.14	70.37
Mutton	14.47	14.71	15.04	15.43	16.17	16.20
Other types of meat	0.63	0.64	0.66	0.66	0.65	0.83

In the global ranking of poultry meat production, Russia has consistently maintained fourth position (4.71 million tons) over the past decade, following the United States (20.47 million tons), China (15.3 million tons), and Brazil (14.18 million tons) (Table 2). However, in terms of production growth rate during 2016-2021, Russia (11.6%) ranks seventh, behind India (28%), Thailand (24.2%), Mexico (18.9%), Turkey (17.8%), the EU (15.7%), China (12.8%), and the United States (12.4%). Russia's contribution to global poultry meat production (135.07 million tons) stands at 5.7% – 4.35 times less than the United States (24.65%), 3.25 times less than China (18.42%), and 3.01 times less than Brazil (17.1%) [27].

Table 2

Top 10 countries – leaders in the production of broiler meat in 2015-2021,
in slaughter weight, million tons

Country	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
USA	18.21	18.51	18.94	19.36	19.94	20.24	20.47
China	13.36	12.45	11.60	11.70	13.75	14.60	15.30
Brazil	13.55	13.52	13.61	13.36	13.69	13.88	14.18
EU	10.89	11.56	11.91	12.26	12.56	12.20	12.60
Russia	4.22	4.33	4.68	4.68	4.67	4.72	4.71
India	3.26	3.46	3.76	4.06	4.35	4.00	4.20
Mexico	3.18	3.28	3.40	3.49	3.60	3.70	3.78
Thailand	2.69	2.81	2.99	3.17	3.30	3.25	3.34
Turkey	1.91	1.88	2.14	2.16	2.14	2.20	2.25
Argentina	2.09	2.12	2.15	2.07	2.17	2.19	2.22

When examining Russian poultry farming by region, the industry is particularly well-developed in the Central and Volga Federal Districts. For many years, the Central Federal District has remained the leader in poultry meat production, accounting for 1.86 million tons in 2020, followed by the Volga Federal District with 1.11 million tons. Together, these two districts produce nearly 60% (2,972 thousand tons) of Russia's total poultry meat output (see Table 3).

Table 3

Poultry meat production in the federal districts of Russia in 2019-2020,
slaughter weight, thousand tons

Federal District	2019		2020	
	Thousand tons	Share, %	Thousand tons	Share, %
Russia	5013.16	100	5030.01	100
Central Federal District	1860.2	37.11	1863.13	37.04
Volga Federal District	1111.8	22.18	1153.63	22.94
North Caucasian Federal District	420.42	8.39	427.17	8.5
Northwestern Federal District	395.1	7.8	405.26	8.06
Ural Federal District	431.71	8.61	394.89	7.85
Southern Federal District	412.16	8.22	391.65	7.79
Northern Federal District	351.75	7.02	360.52	7.17
Far Eastern Federal District	30.02	0.6	33.76	0.7

Another important poultry product is eggs. Eggs contain 12.7% complete protein and play a significant role in human nutrition. Table eggs represent one of the cheapest and most rapidly renewable protein sources, enjoying widespread popularity globally. According to FAO UN and national statistical agencies, global table egg production in 2021 reached 86.9 million tons, remaining stable compared to 2020 levels. Overall, the 2017-2020 period saw global table egg production grow at an average annual rate of 3.3%. China dominates global table egg production, accounting for 38.2% of total output in 2021. The average Chinese citizen consumes 21.8 kg of eggs annually – the highest rate among the top ten producing nations. India, another major producer with approximately 8% of global output, shows the lowest per capita consumption among the top ten producers at just 4.4 kg annually. The EU accounted for 6.8% of global table egg production in 2021. China produced 33.2 million tons of table eggs in 2021, a 1.7% decrease from the previous year. India's production increased by 8.5% to 7 million tons, maintaining an average annual growth rate of 8.6%. EU production grew by 2.5% to 5.9 million tons. Among surveyed countries, Brazil demonstrated the highest production growth rates after India, averaging 8.3% annually from 2017-2021. Russia's 2021 production of 2.4 million tons represented 2.7% of global table egg output (Table 4) [Rosstat].

Table 4

Major food egg-producing countries, 2017-2021, thousand tons

Country	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2021/2020, %
China	30 181	30 493	32 255	33 801	33 228	2.4%
India	5023	5450	5 974	6 433	6 979	8.6%
EU	5 634	5 790	5 793	5 800	5 946	1.4%
USA	5 673	5 722	5 801	5 639	5 494	-0.8%
Indonesia	4 540	4 581	4 659	5 108	5 152	3.2%
Mexico	2641	2 737	2 812	2 875	2 788	1.4%
Brazil	1 876	2 090	2 304	2 518	2 584	8.3%
Japan	2 520	2 546	2 557	2 552	2 495	-0.2%
Russia	2 357	2 357	2 353	2 356	2 358	0.01%
Turkey	1 100	1 121	1 136	1 129	1 101	0.03%
Others	17 304	17 908	18 273	18 802	18 783	2.1%
Total	78 848	80 795	83 916	87 013	86 910	2.5%

When examining production by Russian regions, the Leningrad region leads in egg production, with Rosstat data showing 3,482.5 million eggs produced in 2021 was

the country's highest output. Notably, the Leningrad region continues to expand production, achieving 8.7% growth in 2021. The Yaroslavl region, ranking second, significantly trails the leader, having produced 2,133.3 million chicken eggs in 2021, which was a 10.1% decrease compared to 2020. The Belgorod region ranks third with laying hens producing 1,623.7 million eggs (101.1% of 2020 levels).

The top five regions of Russia for chicken egg production also included the Sverdlovsk and Chelyabinsk regions, where 1,595.3 million and 1,594.6 million eggs were produced, respectively, in 2021. In general, in Russia, by the end of 2021, 44.9 billion chicken eggs were produced (100% of 2020 production levels) [Rosstat].

Table 5

Top 20 regions of the Russian Federation for egg production in 2021,
million pieces

No.	Region	2021	2021/2020, %
1	Leningrad region	3,482.5	108.7
2	Yaroslavl region	2,133.3	89.9
3	Belgorod region	1,623.7	101.1
4	Sverdlovsk region	1,595.3	105.3
5	Chelyabinsk region	1,594.6	97.8
6	Republic of Mordovia	1,555.3	105.4
7	Republic of Tatarstan	1,504.1	102.4
8	Krasnodar Territory	1,501.9	97.5
9	Rostov region.	1,396.6	82.2
10	Tyumen region	1,393	89.4
11	Perm Territory	1,391.3	102.2
12	Nizhny Novgorod region	1,243.7	96.6
13	Kemerovo region	1,214.7	101.8
14	Republic of Bashkortostan	1,125.9	109.3
15	Novosibirsk region.	1,107.1	89
16	Udmurt Republic	1,084.2	99.4
17	Ryazan region	1,014	104.5
18	Altai Territory	1,011.5	99.6
19	Irkutsk region	1,003.7	99.6
20	Orenburg region	994.7	98.6

It should be noted that in Russia approximately 81.2% of eggs are produced by large agricultural organizations, 17.6% – by household farms, and 1.2% – by peasant (farm) enterprises. Additionally, according to Rosstat data, the egg-laying rate of hens in agricultural organizations (excluding small businesses) in 2021 was 310 eggs per hen compared to 313 eggs the previous year.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Poultry farming represents a sector that makes significant contributions not only to the national economy but also to food security by supplying high-quality animal protein essential for maintaining human health. In Russia, as in other countries worldwide, the poultry industry stands as one of the leading agricultural sectors, providing citizens not only with high-quality natural food products but also raw materials for industrial processing (feathers, down, and manure). Annual growth in poultry production is consistently observed. In order to overcome crisis situations and maintain production growth, it is necessary to enhance production efficiency through the implementation of new technologies and reduction of non-productive costs [28]. Equally important is ensuring stable operations of poultry breeding enterprises, as their performance directly impacts the overall success of the poultry industry.

The development of poultry farming in Russia can lead to increased production of poultry meat and eggs, thereby providing the population with quality food products and reducing import dependence. Industry growth may also stimulate regional economic development, create new employment opportunities, and improve living standards. The adoption of modern technologies in poultry farming can enhance production efficiency, improve product quality, and reduce environmental impact. Research and development in poultry nutrition may optimize feed resources, reduce production costs, and increase productivity.

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